

Reinforcement Learning-Based Autonomous Navigation System for a Simulated Mars Rover Craft.

Mr. Chamikara H.M.D^{1*}

¹*Faculty of Information Technology, Horizon Campus, Malabe, Sri Lanka.*

Abstract.

In today's world, technology-based autonomous navigation is a critical requirement for planetary exploration missions such as Mars missions, where communication delays make manual control infeasible. Traditional rule-based systems lack adaptability in dynamic and unpredictable terrains. Reinforcement Learning (RL) offers a promising solution by enabling agents to learn optimal navigation strategies through trial-and-error interactions in simulated environments. This study aims to design and implement an RL-based autonomous navigation system for a simulated Mars rover using Unity ML-Agents. The rover will be trained using the Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) algorithm to perform obstacle avoidance and goal-directed navigation. The expected results include improved adaptability compared to rule-based approaches and the ability to generalize across different terrain configurations. This research contributes to the development of cost-effective, simulation-based frameworks for planetary robotics, reducing risks before real-world deployment.

Keywords: *Reinforcement Learning, Mars Rover, Autonomous Navigation, Unity ML-Agents, PPO.*